

The influence of context in subjective impressions. A case study on the influence of decoration styles in consumer's subjective impressions ceramic flooring

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Abstract Materials perception plays an important role in the subjective impressions (meanings and emotions) that a product can elicit. New research activity to systematically explore the relationship between the attributes of materials and subjective experiences of their multisensory perception is been carried out in the last decade. This paper contributes in this aim providing a two phase study about the impact that the context, through three different decoration styles, has on the subjective impressions evoked by a particular ceramic floor, showed through computer renderings. In the first phase, semantic differential technique was used on a 70 participant on-line survey, whereas a combination of semantic differential and eye-tracking techniques was used in the second phase with 30 participants. Results of the first phase showed that the used decoration styles can influence certain subjective impressions related to the material. This was confirmed by the second experimental study where besides, eye-tracking techniques have also showed some differences in gaze behavior depending on the context, and between women and men.

Keywords *Decoration influence, Ceramic flooring, Eye-tracking, Semantic differential, Subjective impressions*

Introduction

Consumer preferences and behavior have long been a topic of interest for researchers in many disciplines, such as product design, engineering, marketing, or psychology (Veryzer, 2005; Seva, Duh and Helander, 2007). As investigation techniques evolve, new methodologies are developed that can be applied to determine the exact factors that influence consumer decisions. In an era where product functional requirements are regularly met, designers strive to understand the consumer needs located at the highest level of the Jordan's hierarchy (Jordan, 2000), i.e. the subjective impressions (meanings and emotions) that a product can elicit.

Different strategies can be used to measure the meaning and emotions evoked by a product or environment. The Semantic differential technique (Osgood, Suci and Tannenbaum, 1957) is based on product semantics and relies on product assessments using Likert scales with antonym expressions. This is a standard tool to elicit subjective perception about products (Chang and Wu, 2009; Cheng and Chang, 2009).

However, new alternatives in evaluation techniques have been incorporated in design practice in the last years. One of them is the use of neuro-technologies to investigate perception and evoked emotions combined

with semantics measures (Rojas et al., 2015; Piqueras-Fiszman et al., 2013). These new synergies provide a new way to analyze the emotional impact of design, and put aside the speculation of affective process.

Eye-Tracking is a powerful technique to analyze gaze behavior and attention (Rayner, 1998). When we read, look at a scene, or search for an object, we make continuous eye movements called saccades. Important variables can be obtained from these actions. Movement and attention require spending time on the stimulus. These elements are the basis of a number of methods used to filter visual information. Eye movements provide an objective indicator of where a person's overt attention (and usually also their covert) is focused (Hoffman and Subramaniam, 1995; Spence and Driver, 2004). Although several aspects of oculomotor behavior can be used, the locus of an observer's visual fixations is perhaps the single most commonly used parameter when it comes to assessing where a consumer's attention might be focused (Piqueras-Fiszman et al., 2013).

The connection between visual elements and their psychological effects has been a topic under active discussion (Moszkowicz, 2011). Research shows that gaze can capture elements that may psychologically and physiologically influence the observer, as our eyes are connected to emotions and attention can be biased

Figure 1. The four images used in the pilot study. Image d was only used in this phase. Images a, b and c were used in the second phase.

by mood (Joormann and Gotlib, 2007; Kellough, Beevers, Ellis and Wells, 2008). Emotional and cognitive processes can be measured relatively accurately with eye-tracking technology, even when participants are sitting in front of a computer screen (Liu, Lai and Chuang, 2011). Recording gaze data can help us understand judgments related to specific design attributes.

In this paper, we try to explore how our perception of materials is influenced by different decoration styles. Using a case study, we try to assess the impressions evoked by a particular ceramic floor using both subjective techniques (semantic differential) and objective ones (eye-tracking). In both cases we use computer renderings as stimuli to get user perceptual responses. Some products such as furniture or floorings, are widely displayed through renders on internet pages, in advertising, and even also through the stages of the design and development process. Virtual representations provide an interesting framework to experiment with new design alternatives (Söderman, 2005; Serrano, Botella, Baños, & Alcañiz, 2013) and current real time computer graphics technology can provide ultra-realistic renderings where it is difficult to distinguish between real and virtual representations. Regarding the virtual or real nature of the stimuli used to assess user perception, Söderman (2005) concludes that for efficient product evaluations with users there are other factors to consider than the degree of realism in the product representations. For example, that the participants are well familiar with the type of product, but also with the type of representation technology to be used. In other study (Artacho-Ramírez, Diego-Mas, & Alcaide-Marzal, 2008) regarding the realism of the representation, one of the conclusions was that there is a majority of concepts that the product is able to transmit in the same way independently of the type of representation.

Experimental work

Experimental work has been organized in two phases. In the first one, semantic differential was used on a pilot study where an on-line survey (with 70 participants) was used to ask participants about the

subjective impressions evoked by a particular ceramic flooring, presented through different images of a same room, but with different options of furniture and decorative elements (and also without furniture). In phase two, 30 subjects participated on a new study. This time participants' subjective impressions were again analyzed through semantic differential technique, and also their gaze over the ceramic flooring images were measured, using eye-tracking technology. Both studies used high quality computer generated renderings displayed on a computer screen as stimuli. The next sections describe in detail both experiments.

Phase 1: Pilot study

Image selection: ceramic flooring

The ceramic tile flooring was picked from the group of the highest ranked floors from a previous study on the subjective impressions elicited by ceramic tile floorings (Agost and Vergara, 2014). The original rendered image in that study was of a 'neutral' room, with no decorative elements (image "d" in Figure 1). Three other rendered images of the same room were generated, this time with furniture and elements of varied decoration styles. The furniture included a dining table and chairs, a couch, and other complementary elements (see images "a", "b" and "c" in Figure 1).

The same ceramic tile flooring was used in all four images. However, the three furnished ones are seen from a different camera angle from the one used in the original empty room image, where a window and two doors prevent from including the furniture. Consequently, results of the original empty room will be taken into consideration only in this phase of the study, for subjective impression.

Identification of subjective impressions

The selection of subjective impressions is based on the results of the previous study on ceramic flooring (Agost and Vergara, 2014). In that study, the 24 original semantic descriptors considered were reduced to 9 factors (pairs of antonym adjectives), applying factorial analysis. We have adopted these nine pairs of adjectives (see Table 1). Besides, in the cited study the 14 emotional descriptors were reduced to only one, which coincided with the preference. We have now included the emotion (preference) through the assertion "Like flooring". Two other pairs of assertions ("Like decorations"; "Decorations adequacy") regarding decoration preferences have been added, as we want to study decoration influence. The survey was conducted in Spanish (participants' first language) (see Table 1). Each pair of antonym assertions was further explained in the survey instructions.

Participants were asked to assess each pair of assertions using a 5-point Likert scale. During the analysis phase, the scale ratings were adjusted to -2 to +2. The first assertion in each pair corresponds to the highest value in the score.

Survey: participants and materials

The survey was conducted via on-line questionnaires.

Participants included university staff, their relatives, and acquaintances. Seventy responses were recorded (39 men and 31 women). Each participant was randomly assigned one of the four possible images (see Figure 1) and asked to assess the subjective impressions elicited by the ceramic flooring, by rating the scales of the pairs of assertions (Table 1). Thus, all participants were asked to assess the same ceramic flooring, regardless of the room decoration style assigned. Eighteen responses were recorded for image "a", 19 responses for image "b", 18 responses for image "c", and 15 responses for image "d".

Data analysis

First we have analyzed whether the responses of the 9 pairs of antonym adjectives, which represent the judgment of the floorings, affect the flooring preferences (the assertion "Like flooring") or even with the decoration preferences (the other two questions "Like decorations" and "Decorations adequacy"). To gain insight about these preferences, correlation coefficients were calculated between the responses of the 9 pairs of antonym adjectives shown in Table 1, and the pair of assertions showing preference: "Like flooring". Additional correlation coefficients were calculated between "Like flooring" and the other two questions about preferences: "Like decorations" and "Decorations adequacy". The Spearman coefficient was used, because the variables did not follow a normal distribution (Kolmogorov-Smirnov test results revealed significant differences with normal distribution, $p < 0.05$, for all variables).

Second, we have analyzed whether the judgment of the floorings (adjective assessments) are influenced by the type of decoration, in order to conclude that decoration styles can influence subjective impressions of the floorings. As variables cannot be assumed to follow a normal distribution, Kruskal-Wallis tests were applied in order to check the influence of the type of decoration on the 11 assessments related to the subjective impressions evoked by the flooring (independent variable: type of decoration; dependent variables: assessment ratings to each pair of

assertions -subjective impressions-). When the Kruskal-Wallis test showed significant differences, the Mann-Whitney U test for two independent samples was applied. Bonferroni adjustment was considered in order to control the error rate (the probability of making type I errors). Since the four type of decoration need six pair comparisons (1-2, 1-3, 1-4, 2-3, 2-4, 3-4), Bonferroni adjustment leads to a critical significance level for the decision of $p = 0.05/6 = 0.0083$.

Results of pilot study

The Spearman correlation coefficients between the adjectives and the question about preference ("Like flooring") are shown in Table 2. It can be observed that only the adjectives with a symbolic meaning maintain a significant correlation with "Like flooring", while adjectives with a more functional meaning do not correlate with this assessment. This result agrees with the previous study (Agost and Vergara, 2014).

The Spearman correlation coefficients between "Like flooring" and the rest of preferences are shown in Table 3. Flooring preference is significantly correlated with a taste for the decorations, but it is not with the adequacy of the decorations. In other words, it seems reasonable to choose decorations based on subjective impressions, regardless of their adequacy for the specific type of flooring.

The Kruskal-Wallis test shows that significant differences (significance value $p < 0.05$) can be considered between types of decoration for some adjectives: "Versatile" (significance value $p = 0.41$), "Innovative" ($p < 0.001$), "Bright" ($p = 0.037$), and "Expensive looking" ($p = 0.037$). However, the subsequent application of the Mann-Whitney U test for two samples (taking critical significance level = 0.0083) shows that only significant difference is identified in the assessment of "Innovative" between decorations "a" and "b" ($p = < 0.001$) and between decoration "a" and image "d" ($p = 0.002$) (see Figure 2). Nevertheless, as it has been previously pointed, differences identified between a furnished image and image "d" will not be considered.

Table 1. Pairs of antonym assertions representing subjective impressions used in the pilot study.

Subjective Impressions		
(A: Adjective/ P: Preference)	Spanish words	Translation
A: Versatile	Sencillo, versatile/Recargado, poco adaptable	Simple, versatile/Excessively ornate, not adaptable
A: Innovative	Innovador/ Tradicional	Innovative / Traditional
A: Bright	Luminoso/ Apagado	Bright/Dark
A: Resistant	Resistente/ Frágil	Resistant/ Fragile
A: Easy to clean	Fácil limpieza/Difícil limpieza	Easy to clean/Difficult to clean
A: Cosy	Hogareño/ Poco domestico	Cosy/ Not cosy
A: Expensive	Aspecto de caro/ Aspecto barato	Expensive looking/ Cheap looking
A: Natural	Natural/ Artificial	Natural/ Artificial
A: Elegant	Elegante/Vulgar	Elegant/ Ordinary
P: Flooring	Me gusta el pavimento/ no me gusta	I like the flooring/ I do not like it
P: Decorations	Me gusta la decoración / No me gusta	I like decorations/ I do not like them
P: Decorations adequacy	El mobiliario y el resto de elementos decorativos son adecuados para el pavimento de la estancia: Muy adecuados/ Nada adecuados	The furniture and the rest of decorative elements are suitable for the room flooring: Very appropriate/ Not suitable

In this particular case, the decoration style used can influence the assessment of the floor innovation. Results of this pilot study show that the decoration style used can influence certain subjective impressions related to the flooring.

Therefore, it was decided to perform a second phase of the study. This time the aim was applying the semantic differential technique, and also eye-tracking technology, in order to check if differences were detected again, not only in subjective assessments, but also in objective parameters measured in participants' gaze behaviour.

Although the adjectives correlated with the ceramic flooring preference are in general those of symbolic meaning, it was decided to consider again also those with functional meaning, to avoid losing information. On the other side, the image of the empty room ("d") was removed, since it does not reproduce the same view of the room, and therefore it cannot be compared with the other three images.

Phase 2: application of semantic differential and eye-tracking techniques

In phase 2, an eye-tracking system was incorporated to the study to measure participant gaze over the ceramic flooring images. Thirty subjects participated (14 men and 16 women). Ten participants were assigned to each of the three furnished images used for the ceramic flooring assessment. The reason of using a small sample is due to recent studies that predict efficient outcomes with eye-tracking and other techniques combined (Fehd and Seiffert, 2008; Galotto and Ulloa, 2010; Liu, Lai and Chuang, 2011; Kwon and Sturt, 2014; Mitterer-Daltoé et al., 2014). The stimuli for the eye-tracking system were produced by combining each furnished room image (1200x900 pixels) with the semantic scales, as shown in Figure 3. Twelve stimuli were produced per image, one for each subjective impression in the questionnaire (see Table 1).

Procedure

Stimuli were displayed in a Tobii device (Tobii® TX300, www.tobii.com), with a 23" HD screen and the Tobii tracker located below the screen. The study was conducted in a room free from distractions, where

Figure 2. Confidence intervals (95%) for the mean. Assessment of "Innovative" (phase 1).

participants sat on a comfortable chair with the eye-tracking device system in front of them during a single session of no more than 10 minutes. The process is illustrated in Figure 4.

Initially, participants were given a personal questionnaire (so the research team could obtain demographic data), and listened to the test instructions. Next, they performed a gaze calibration guided by Tobii system followed by 20 second slide on the screen with the test instructions. After a five second delay, the study was launched. Each participant was randomly presented with the questions related to exactly one of the images shown in Figure 3. Stimuli were displayed on the screen for a limited amount of time based in similar studies (Jacob

Table 3. Correlations between preferences.

Correlation between "I like flooring/ I do not like it" and...	Spearman coefficient (p)
I like decorations/ I do not like them	0.463** (0.000)
Decorations adequacy: The furniture and the rest of decorative elements are suitable for the room flooring: Very appropriate/ Not suitable	0.228 (0.094)

Table 2. Spearman correlation coefficients between adjectives and flooring preference ("Like flooring").

Adjectives significantly correlated to "I like the flooring/ I do not like it" (Signification level < 0.05)	Spearman coefficient (p)	Adjectives not correlated to "I like the flooring/ I do not like it"	Spearman coefficient (p)
Natural/ Artificial	0.487** (0.000)	Expensive looking/ Cheap looking	0.168 (0.165)
Simple, versatile/ Excessively ornate, not adaptable	0.482** (0.000)	Brigth/Dark	0.144 (0.233)
Cosy/ Not cosy	0.416** (0.000)	Resistant/ Fragile	-0.103 (0.407)
Innovative / Traditional	0.414** (0.000)	Easy to clean/Difficult to clean	-0.002 (0.985)
Elegant/ Ordinary	0.404** (0.000)		

Figure 3. Stimulus (image and semantic scale) as shown to participants in our study. Images "a, b and c".

Figure 4. Complete process scheme.

and Karn [2003] suggests a minimum of 100-200 milliseconds to obtain fixation data and verify sample rates of eye-tracking device).

The test was structured in two clusters: cluster A and B. The cluster A is comprised consecutively by the nine image/scale, the response time screen and the break screen. The stimuli "image/scale" were displayed for 3 to 5 seconds and the "response time" was displayed until the participants answered. The "break" screen displayed a white screen for 1 second. The cluster B is comprised consecutively by the three questions screen related to the decoration, the three image/scale, the response time screen and break screen. When the two clusters ended a screen informed about the end of test.

Data analysis

The eye-tracking system records various parameters from the observer, such as visual routes and heat maps, which can help identify relevant areas of the scene.

Visual routes are a representation of visual behavior, which exposes where the gaze of the subject was fixed at each moment, and the followed path. The visual routes for one participant and for all participants for

a given stimulus are shown in Figure 5.

Heat maps are a static representation of the analysis of visual patterns for a set of subjects. The heat maps for a participant and for all participants for a given stimulus are shown in Figure 5. To quantitatively analyze the ET results, we defined areas of interest (AOIs) for each image, differentiating between areas related to the ceramic flooring from areas containing decorative elements. The AOIs for each image are shown in Figure 6.

The time spent looking at different AOIs was extracted and the percentage of time spent looking at the flooring area was calculated (for each question, total seconds looking at the flooring area / total seconds looking at the stimulus, before answering). Reading time was not considered. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test showed that variables cannot be considered to follow a normal distribution both for semantic differential data and percentage of time from eye-tracking.

As in the previous pilot phase, for the semantic differential data we have analyzed whether the judgment of the floorings (adjective assessments) are

Figure 5. In the left column: visual routes of a participant (top) and the 10 participants (bottom) that were assigned to image "a". In the right column: heat map of a participant (top) and of the 10 participants (bottom) to same image.

Figure 6. Areas of interest (AOIs) assigned to the images.

influenced by the type of decoration, to conclude that decoration styles can influence subjective impressions of the floorings. A Kruskal-Wallis test was applied to find out whether there were significant differences in the assessments, depending on the type of decoration (independent variable: type of decoration; dependent variables: assessment ratings to each pair of assertions -subjective impressions-). When the Kruskal-Wallis test showed significant differences, the Mann-Whitney U test for two independent samples was applied. Bonferroni adjustment was considered in order to control the probability of making type I errors. Since the 3 types of decoration need 3 pair comparisons (1-2, 1-3, 2-3), Bonferroni adjustment leads to a critical significance level for the decision of

$$p = 0.05/3 = 0.0166.$$

For the eye-tracking data, we have analyzed whether the judgment of the floorings (adjective assessments) are influenced by the time spent looking at the decoration areas, for each type of decoration. To check the possible influence of the types of decoration, the Spearman correlation coefficient between each rating assessment and the percentage of time looking at the decoration areas before answering (1 - the percentage of time looking at the flooring area) was calculated separately for each type of decoration. Additional application of the Kruskal-Wallis tests was performed to compare the assessments and gaze behavior, taking the type of decoration as the independent variable. The

Figure 7. Confidence intervals (95%) for the mean. Left: Assessment of "Innovative" (phase 2). Right: Percentage of time looking at decorations areas before assessing "Like flooring" (phase 2).

Mann-Whitney U test was also applied to compare women and men results (independent variable: gender).

Results

The Kruskal-Wallis test showed a significance value $p=0.034$ (<0.05) for "Innovative", so that significant differences in this assessment are found based on the type of decoration also in this second phase, although with a lower number of respondents. The subsequent application of the Mann-Whitney U test for two samples shows significant differences between images "a" and "b" ($p=0.035$) and between "b" and "c" ($p=0.029$), although significance values are higher than the adjusted critical significance level ($p=0.0166$). Figure 7 (left) shows the confidence intervals (95%) for the mean of "Innovative" assessment, for the 3 images.

In terms of the objective parameters obtained from eye-tracking, the Kruskal-Wallis test showed a significance value $p=0.038$ (<0.05) for the percentage of time looking at decoration AOIs before assessing "Like flooring", based on the type of decoration. The subsequent application of the Mann-Whitney U test for two samples shows significant difference between images "a" and "c" ($p=0.015$ <0.0166). This difference is shown in Figure 7 (right).

Besides, correlation coefficients between the assessment to each question and the percentage of time looking at the decoration AOIs before answering are only statistically significant between the percentage of time looking at decoration AOIs and the assessment of "Innovative" for image "a" (Figure 1) (Spearman coefficient: 0.636; $p=0.048$). That is to say, the more time spent looking at decorations, the more innovative the assessment for the ceramic flooring. This objective fact also seems to align with the idea that the decoration type influences the ceramic flooring perception.

Results of the semantic differential and eye-tracking analysis also reveal behavioral differences between men and women. Regarding to semantic differential analysis, the Mann-Whitney U test shows significant differences between women and men in the assessment of "Bright" and also in the assessment of "Like flooring" ($p=0.038$ and $p=0.043$ respectively).

Women seem to perceive the flooring brighter ($M_{\text{women}}=1.13$; $M_{\text{men}}=0.29$) and do not like the flooring while men do ($M_{\text{women}}=-0.56$; $M_{\text{men}}=0.5$).

Regarding eye-tracking data, significant differences have been also detected between women and men (Mann-Whitney U test) when answering the questions "Bright" and "Decorations adequacy". In particular, women spend a lower percentage of time looking at the decorative elements before answering to these questions than men do. The average percentage of time looking decorative areas before answering "Bright" are: $M_{\text{women}}=43.18\%$; $M_{\text{men}}=57.76\%$, and before answering about the decoration adequacy: $M_{\text{women}}=64.76\%$; $M_{\text{men}}=82.90\%$.

In addition, women make a higher percentage of visits to the ceramic flooring area than men do when answering "Decorations adequacy". The average percentages of times looking at the ceramic flooring are $M_{\text{women}}=36.53\%$, $M_{\text{men}}=17.12\%$. So, in the assessment of the context adequacy, women focus more on looking at the material, while men do in the decorative elements.

The results obtained are affected by the small sample size. The power of the analysis is limited, so that only very high differences have been detected as significant. That is to say, the probability of making type II errors in the analysis is very high; we have not probably found all the existing significant differences.

Conclusions

In this paper, we describe the results of a study designed to analyze the influence of different decoration styles on the subjective impressions evoked by a particular ceramic floor. The material is assessed through rendered images with different decorative elements. In the first phase, semantic differential technique was applied, whereas a combination of semantic differential and eye-tracking techniques was used in the second phase.

Results of the first phase showed that the decoration style used where a material is presented can influence certain subjective impressions related to the material. In our particular case, the rating assessment of the adjective "Innovative" for the ceramic flooring was

significantly different between two different decorations (images “a” and “b”).

The second phase of the study incorporated eye-tracking technique in order to check whether differences were detected again, not only in subjective assessments, but also in objective parameters measured in participants’ gaze behavior. Results showed a significant correlation between the percentage of time looking at the decoration areas for a particular decoration (image “a”) and the assessment for the adjective “Innovative”. This objective fact also seems to align with the idea that the decoration type influences the ceramic flooring perception. Due to the small sample size, the power of the analysis is limited. Consequently, we have probably made type II errors (we have not probably found existing significant differences). Eye-tracking techniques have also showed some differences in gaze behavior between women and men.

Based on the results of our study, we can conclude that the decoration style used where a material is presented can influence some subjective impressions evoked by the product in which that material is employed. The combination of the semantic differential with eye-tracking provide both subjective and objective measures of the impact of this contextual influence, giving a valuable information that can be taken into account to improve the design or customize it according to some specific group of users.

Finally, although the techniques used are based on different-natured data (subjective data, in the semantic differential technique, and objective data in ET), the results are related: in both cases a significant difference has been detected in the assessment of the image ‘a’ for the meaning ‘Innovative’. This result opens a new field of future work: to find the possible equivalence or complementarity of subjective and objective measurement techniques, in affective design.

References

- Agost, M.J., Vergara, M. (2014). Relationship between meanings, emotions, product preferences and personal values. Application to ceramic tile floorings. *Applied Ergonomics*, 45, 1076–1086.
- Artacho-Ramírez, M. A., Diego-Mas, J. A., Alcaide-Marzal, J. (2008). Influence of the mode of graphical representation on the perception of product aesthetic and emotional features: An exploratory study. *International Journal of Industrial Ergonomics*, 38(11-12), 942-952.
- Chang, C.C. Wu, J.C. (2009). The underlying factors dominating categorical perception of product form of mobile phones. *International Journal of Industrial Ergonomics*, 39(5), 667-680.
- Cheng, H.Y., Chang, Y.M. (2009). Extraction of product form features critical to determining consumers’ perceptions of product image using a numerical definition-based systematic approach. *International Journal of Industrial Ergonomics*, 39(1), 133-145.
- Fehd, H. M., Seiffert, A. E. (2008). Eye movements during multiple object tracking: Where do participants look? *Cognition*, 108(1), 201-209.
- Galotto, M., Ulloa, P. (2010). Effect of high pressure food processing on the mass transfer properties of selected packaging materials. *Packaging and Technology and Science*, 23, 253-266.
- Hoffman, J., Subramaniam, B. (1995). The role of visual attention in saccadic eye movements. *Perception & Psychophysics*, 57, 787-795.
- Joormann, J., Gotlib, I. H. (2007). Selective attention to emotional faces following recovery from depression. *Journal of Abnormal Psychology*, 116, 80-85.
- Jacob, R., Karn, K. (2003). Cometary: Eye tracking in human-computer interaction and usability research: ready to deliver the promises. In *The mind's eye Cognitive and applied aspects of eye movement research* (pp. 573-605). Elsevier Science Inc.
- Jordan, P. W. (2000). *Designing Pleasurable Products. An introduction to the new human factors*. London, Taylor and Francis.
- Kellough, J. L., Beevers, C. G., Ellis, A. J., Wells, T.T. (2008). Time course of selective attention in clinically depressed young adults: An eye tracking study. *Behaviour Research and Therapy*, 46(11), 1238-1243.
- Kwon, N., Sturt, P. (2014). The use of control information in dependency formation: An eye-tracking study. *Journal of Memory and Language*, 73(1), 59-80.
- Liu, H.C., Lai, M. L., Chuang, H. H. (2011). Using eye-tracking technology to investigate the redundant effect of multimedia web pages on viewers’ cognitive processes. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 27, 2410-2417.
- Mitterer-Daltoé, M. L., Queiroz, M. I., Fiszman, S., Varela, P. (2014). Are fish products healthy? Eye tracking as a new food technology tool for a better understanding of consumer perception. *LWT - Food Science and Technology*, 55(2), 459-465.
- Mozzkowicz, J. (2011). Gestalt and Graphic Design: an exploration of the humanistic and therapeutic effects of visual organization. *Design Issues*, 27(4), 56-67.
- Osgood C.E., Suci G.J. Tannenbaum P.H. (1957). *The Measurement of Meaning*. University of Illinois, Press, IL.
- Piqueras-Fiszman, B., Velasco, C., Salgado-Montejo, A., Spence, C. (2013). Using combined eye tracking and word association in order to assess novel packaging solutions: A case study involving jam jars. *Food Quality and Preference*, 28(1), 328–338.
- Rayner, K. (1998). Eye Movements in Reading and Information Processing: 20 Years of Research. *Psychological bulletin*, 124(3), 372-422.

Rojas, J. C., Contero, M., Bartomeu, N., & Guixeres, J. (2015). Using Combined Bipolar Semantic Scales and Eye-Tracking Metrics to Compare Consumer Perception of Real and Virtual Bottles. *Packaging Technology and Science*, 28 (12), 1047-1056. Serrano, B., Botella, C., Baños, R. M., Alcañiz, M. (2013). Using virtual reality and mood-induction procedures to test products with consumers of ceramic tiles. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 29(3), 648-653.

Seva, R. R., Duh, H. B. L., Helander, M. G. (2007). The marketing implications of affective product design. *Applied Ergonomics*, 38, 723-731.

Söderman, M. (2005). Virtual reality in product evaluations with potential customers: An exploratory study comparing virtual reality with conventional product representations. *Journal of Engineering Design*, 16(3), 311-328. Spence, C., Driver, J. (Eds.). (2004). *Crossmodal space and crossmodal attention*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Veryzer, R. V. (2005). The role of marketing and industrial design in discontinuous new product development. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 22, 22-41.

Wardono, P., Hibino, H. Koyama, S. (2012). Effects of Interior Colors, Lighting and Decors on Perceived Sociability, Emotion and Behavior Related to Social Dining. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 38, 362-372.